

MANAGEMENT OF SCALE-UP RESEARCH PROJECTS FOR DEVELOPING NOVEL ADSORPTIVE MATERIALS BASED ON BIO-WASTE RECYCLING AND PROCESSING

F.A. Batzias, O. Kopsidas, D. Karalekas, A. Bountri
 Laboratory of Simulation of Industrial Processes,
 Department of Industrial Management and Technology,
 University of Piraeus
 Karaoli & Dimitriou 80, 18534 Piraeus Greece
 Tel.: +302104142368; Fax: +302104142392; email: fbatzi@unipi.gr

ABSTRACT: This work deals with a project management approach to R&D scale-up research projects, for developing novel adsorptive materials based on bio-waste Recycling and Processing. For this purpose, we have designed a methodological framework, under the form of an algorithmic procedure, including 12 activity stages and 4 decision nodes. Subsequently, we use properly modified fuzzy CPM (Critical Path Method) and PERT (Project Evaluation and Review Technique) for analyzing the stage of waste biomass modification/processing, which is of strategic importance for the rest (upstream and downstream) stages. The functionality of the suggested herein procedure is proved by implementing it in the cases of developing novel adsorptive materials based on wheat straw and sawdust, for which there is adequate experience in our Laboratory.

Keywords: waste, recycling, adsorbent, project development, management

1 INTRODUCTORY ANALYSIS

This work deals with the application of project management methods in biomass research for developing waste-to-energy processes and novel materials based on bio-waste recycling, putting emphasis on the substitution of currently used adsorbents with low-cost and high-availability new ones. For this purpose, we have designed a methodological framework, under the form of an algorithmic procedure, including the following activity stages and decision nodes (denoted by a Latin letter in parenthesis or a number in brackets, respectively), interconnected as shown in the corresponding diagram of Fig. 1. This diagram suggests that a novel material is not proposed, if the waste-to-energy path is dominant nowadays; nevertheless, a global demand side analysis may reveal tendencies towards new materials (or even food). Thus, a more dynamic approach is indispensable.

(A): GIS-aided waste biomass recording (per species) in the wider region under consideration.

(B): Selection of proper waste bio-species per sub-region, occurring in adequate quantities to form reliable raw bio-waste material for a downstream biomass-to-energy industrial unit.

(C): Bio-waste collection.

(D): Bio-waste transportation.

(E): Bio-waste storing.

(F): Waste biomass modification/processing.

(G): Product logistics.

(H): Product utilization.

(I): Waste logistics.

(J): Waste recycle.

(K): Waste incineration.

(L): Waste disposal.

[I]: Are there proper bio-waste species?

[II]: Are the respective bio-waste species adequate in quantity and supply rate in the long-run in order to support production within the downstream unit higher than the breakeven point (on condition of market availability)?

[III]: Is the waste going to recycle or incineration or disposal (denoted by r, i, d, respectively) stage?

[IV]: Is the waste going to incineration or disposal stage?

Figure 1: The methodological framework we have designed under the form of an algorithmic procedure for applying a project management approach in developing waste-to-energy processes and novel materials based on bio-waste recycling.

2 METHODOLOGY

We use properly modified fuzzy CPM (Critical Path Method) and PERT (Project Evaluation and Review Technique) for analyzing stage (F), which is of strategic importance for the rest (upstream and downstream) stages; the corresponding activities are described at Table I, where each one of them is represented by two numbers in parenthesis, the first signifying the beginning and the second one signifying the completion of the activity.

Table I: Activities that take place within stage F (biomass processing), as shown in the network.

Activity	Description
(1,2)	System (herein batch process) design.*
(1,3)	Determination of required specifications.
(2,4)	Tolerance design.*
(2,5)	Parameter design.*
(5,6)	Special mixing design.
(6,7)	Biomass transfer, weighting, milling.
(7,8)	Biomass mixing and storing.
(8,9)	Sampling, testing.
(9,10)	Selection of criteria for comparative evaluation of biomass modification methods.
(9,11)	Collection of biomass modification methods.
(11,12)	Evaluation of the elements of the multicriteria preference matrix.
(12,13)	Multicriteria analysis.
(13,14)	Design of batch experiments on kinetics/isotherms [1,2].
(14,15)	Performing of experimental work and processing of results for parameter-values estimation.
(15,16)	Design of experiments for estimating thermodynamic parameter-values.
(16,17)	Performing of experimental work and processing of results for parameter-values estimation.
(17,18)	Determination of required specifications.
(17,19)	Column process design.*
(19,20)	Tolerance design.*
(19,21)	Parameter design.*
(21,22)	Design of column experiments on kinetics and isotherms [1,2].
(22,23)	Performing of experimental work and processing of results for parameter-values estimation.
(23,24)	(Gray box) modeling by means of dimensional analysis.
(23,25)	(Black box) modeling by means of empirical techniques.
(23,26)	(White box) mechanistic modeling.
(26,27)	Testing.
(27,28)	Comparison.
(28,29)	Meta-analysis based on a holistic approach to decide on the necessity of proceeding with a next/upper scale.

*in the sense of Taguchi terminology for quality engineering

The corresponding network (Fig. 2), created by performing the basic phases of planning/scheduling/controlling, consists of 28 real and 7 dummy activities.

3 IMPLEMENTATION

The functionality of the procedure presented herein is proved by implementing it in the case of developing novel adsorptive materials based on wheat straw and sawdust, for which there is adequate experience in our Laboratory. The intermediate and final arithmetic results for PERT are shown in Tables II and III. Estimated total project time:370.88 for PERT and 373.57 for fuzzy CPM.

Figure 2. Arrow/network diagram representing the activities that take place within stage (F), i.e., biomass processing, of a R&D project for developing novel adsorptive materials based on bio-waste recycling. Each arrow represents a unique activity with its head indicating the direction of progress of the project. Each event (boxed number) represents a point in time that signifies the completion of some activities and the beginning of new ones. The dummy activities, $D_1, D_2, D_4, D_5, D_6, D_7$ are used to establish correct precedence activities; D_3 is used to identify activities (namely, ‘collection of biomass modification methods’, ‘selection of criteria for comparative evaluation of biomass modification methods’) that have common start and end events.

Table II: Fuzzy and stochastic duration. Centr. : Crisp number obtained by defuzzification with the centroid method for fuzzy-CPM. Var.: Variance of earliest expected duration (Exp.) for PERT (*): critical activity.

Activity	Centr.	Exp.	Var.
1,2*	12.167	11.933	0.538
1,3	14.033	14.167	0.360
2,4	3.567	3.483	0.047
2,5*	5.567	5.683	0.123
5,6*	11.767	11.883	0.267
6,7*	27.367	27.283	0.967
7,8*	4.867	4.783	0.123
8,9*	19.633	19.367	0.810
9,10	7.933	7.967	0.160
9,11*	9.400	9.300	0.321
11,12*	24.000	23.900	1.604
12,13*	2.600	2.550	0.014
13,14*	6.100	6.100	0.054
14,15*	50.500	49.600	2.668
15,16*	4.033	4.017	0.023
16,17*	37.266	37.083	1.480
17,18	10.5	10.35	0.340
17,19*	15.366	15.333	0.284
19,20	4.233	4.166	0.04
19,21*	5.666	5.633	0.04
21,22*	8.166	8.283	0.146
22,23*	57.366	57.133	1.69
23,24	6.866	6.983	0.100
23,25	12.533	12.516	0.613
23,26*	28.6	28.65	1.322
26,27*	22.9	22.5	1.69
27,28*	7.133	7.066	0.134
28,29*	13.1	12.8	0.64

Table III: Earliest time, variance of earliest time, scheduled time (Earl., VET, Sched., respectively, in hours) and probability (Pr.) of [Earl. > Sched.] per event.

Event	Earl.	VET	Sched.	Pr.
1	0.000	0.000	0	0.000
2	11.930	0.538	12	0.464
3	14.170	0.360	26	0.000
4	15.420	0.047	15	0.973
5	16.620	0.660	18	0.319
6	29.500	0.927	30	0.302
7	56.780	1.894	59	0.054
8	61.570	2.017	63	0.156
9	80.930	2.827	79	0.875
10	88.900	0.160	87	1.000
11	90.230	3.148	91	0.333
12	114.130	4.752	116	0.196
13	116.680	4.766	119	0.144
14	122.780	4.820	126	0.071
15	172.380	7.488	175	0.169
16	176.400	7.511	180	0.094
17	213.480	8.991	219	0.033
18	223.830	0.340	228	0.000
19	228.820	9.275	231	0.237
20	232.980	0.040	232	1.000
21	234.450	9.315	237	0.202
22	242.730	9.462	245	0.231
23	299.870	11.152	296	0.877
24	306.850	0.100	300	1.000
25	312.380	0.614	310	0.999
26	328.520	12.475	337	0.008
27	351.020	14.165	350	0.606
28	358.080	14.299	362	0.150
29	370.880	14.939	375	0.143

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUDING REMARKS

The project completion time X (considered as the independent/stochastic variable) optimization is achieved by minimizing total cost C consisted of two conflict partial variables C_1 and C_2 , representing cost of stage (F) and cost of the rest downstream stages, respectively: the higher the cost C_1 , due to performing more scale-up effort, the lower the cost C_2 , due to producing lower-cost of higher-quality product. X_{opt} is estimated at $C_{min}=(C_1+C_2)_{min}$ as an equilibrium point of this tradeoff, allowing for sensitivity/robustness analysis to examine the influence/impact of endogenous and exogenous factors, like the accumulation of experience in the time course (known as ‘learning by doing’) and the increase of oil prices in the long run, respectively. C_1 is a stepwise function, corresponding to five scale-up levels of experimentation: Lab, Bench, Pre-pilot, Pilot, Prototype. Equipment of the first four scales is shown in Fig.4 [3,4].

Figure 3. Dependence of cost C on project completion time X and determination of X_{opt} at $C_{min} = (C_1 + C_2)_{min}$.

Figure 4: Adsorption columns (top) of stainless steel at lab/bench scale and (bottom) of polymethyl-methacrylate (PMMA) at Pre-pilot (in the right hand side) and pilot scale, adsorbing methylene blue on modified biomass.

Figure 5: Dependence of Expenditure E on Activity Duration T during compression, and sifting of T_{opt} , when (a) the rate of interest decreases and (b) law clauses become stricter.

Within the same activity at a certain scale-up level, the duration T can be compressed by increasing the allocated resources and, consequently, the corresponding expenditure E . Evidently, there is a limit, called ‘crash time’ [5], beyond which no further reduction in the duration can be effected because of technical constraints. We can determine optimal duration T_{opt} at $T_{min} = (T_1 + T_2)_{min}$, where T_1 is the indirect expenditure due to fiscal policy at both, macroeconomic and microeconomic/sectoral levels, and E_2 is the direct expenditure for the resources to be used. E_1 is an increasing function of T with an increasing rate (i.e.,

$dE_1/dT > 0$ and $d^2E_1/dT^2 > 0$), since risk and consequently the corresponding cost of money increases disproportionately in the region of high T -values. On the contrary, is a decreasing function of T with an increasing algebraic or decreasing absolute rate (i.e., $dE_2/dT < 0$ and $d^2E_2/dT^2 > 0$ or $d|dE_2/dT|/dT < 0$) because of the validity of the Law of Diminishing Returns. The T_{opt} -value is determined at $d(E_1 + E_2)/dT = 0$ or $ME_1 = ME_2$, where $ME_1 = dE_1/dT$ and $ME_2 = |dE_2/dT|$ are the marginal values of E_1 and E_2 , respectively.

In case of rate of interest decrease (e.g., when offensive policymaking has been chosen to combat recession in the economic cycle, as shown in [6]), the E_1 -curve moves downwards by parallel shifting, leaving T_{opt} unchanged, as shown in Fig. 5a. In the case of law clauses becoming stricter (e.g., when outsourcing, which involves contracting out of some biomass research activities), implying higher expenditure under the form of expected economic penalties, the E_2 -curve moves upwards becoming steeper at the same time, because failure of cooperation with the external R&D subcontractor is mostly expected in the region of low T -values (where exists also the ‘crash time’ point) due to high compression, as a result, T_{opt} is shifting to where T'_{opt} where $T'_{opt} > T_{opt}$, as shown in Fig. 5b.

In conclusion, a project management approach to R&D scale-up research projects, for developing novel adsorptive materials based on bio-waste Recycling and Processing, may contribute to (i) structuring a methodological framework under the form of an algorithmic procedure to optimize biomass exploitation in the short run and (ii) perform network analysis, including multicriteria optimization in the long run. The functionality of the latter approach is proved by using a numerical case example through PERT while the alternative of using a fuzzy-CPM scheme (in order to take into account subjective reasoning) is also indicated.

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